
The Sri Lankan Adaptation of the Satisfaction with Life Scale (SWLS): Factorial Structure, Gender and Age Invariance in a Sample of Adults

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Abstract

This study adapted the Satisfaction with Life Scale into Sinhala for use in Sri Lanka (SWLS-SL) and evaluated its psychometric properties. A non-probability sample of 303 Sinhala-speaking adults aged 18–79 years ($M_{age} = 40.19$, $SD = 13.54$; 44.4% male, 54.7% female, 1.0% transgender) completed the scale. The hypothesised unidimensional structure was tested using confirmatory factor analysis (CFA), and measurement invariance across gender and age groups was examined using multi-group CFA.

The SWLS-SL demonstrated good reliability (Cronbach's $\alpha = .90$) and strong temporal stability over a two-week interval ($r = .83$, $p < .001$). CFA supported the unidimensional model, $\chi^2(3) = 5.68$, $p = .128$, $CFI = 1.00$, $TLI = .99$, $RMSEA = .05 [0.00, 0.12]$, with correlated residuals between Items 1–2 and 3–4. The model showed strict invariance across gender and strong invariance across age groups. Convergent validity was supported by a positive correlation with the WHO-5 Well-Being Index ($r = .36$, $p < .001$), indicating a modest association.

These findings provide evidence that psychological instruments developed in Western cultural contexts can demonstrate sound psychometric properties in non-Western languages and settings. The psychometric properties of SWLS-SL enable it to be used in the Sinhala-speaking adult population in Sri Lanka to assess satisfaction with life across genders and ages, adding to the limited number of psychological instruments as a measure of an individual's positive orientation, which could have applications in both clinical and social settings.

Keywords: Satisfaction with Life Scale, Sinhala, Sri Lanka, factor structure, measurement invariance, confirmatory factor analysis

Introduction

Satisfaction with life is a central cognitive component of subjective well-being, with applications in distinguishing psychiatric from non-psychiatric populations, monitoring therapeutic change, assessing psychological well-being, and identifying risk for self-harm and psychopathology (Pavot & Diener, 2008). The Satisfaction With Life Scale (SWLS), a five-item measure rated on a seven-point Likert scale (Diener et al., 1985), is among the most widely used instruments of global life satisfaction (Guitard et al., 2022; Hultell & Gustavsson, 2008; Pavot & Diener, 2008), with translations into 39 languages (Arrindell et al., 2022).

Evidence generally supports the psychometric properties of the SWLS. Internal consistency ranges from $\alpha = .60$ to $.90$, and temporal stability from $r = .54$ to $.83$ (Bacro et al., 2020; Jang et al., 2017; Pavot & Diener, 1993, 2008). Confirmatory factor analyses consistently support a unidimensional structure across diverse populations (e.g., Aishvarya et al., 2014; Bacro et al., 2020; Checa et al., 2019; Di Fabio & Gori, 2016; Erdem, 2022; Esnaola et al., 2017; Espejo et al., 2022; Jovanović et al., 2020; García-Castro, 2022; Sancho et al., 2014; Theodoropoulou, 2021; Vázquez et al., 2013).

However, item-level concerns persist. Items 4 and 5 have shown weaker correlations, potentially reducing reliability (Amtmann et al., 2019; Bai et al., 2011; Whisman & Judd, 2016), and tend to yield the lowest item-total correlations and factor loadings (Arrindell et al., 1991; Diener et al., 1985; Oishi, 2006; Pavot & Diener, 1993; Pons et al., 2000).

Most research findings have not supported strict invariance (Emerson et al., 2017), and invariance was more across gender than age

(Arrindell et al., 2022; Bacro et al., 2020; Jang et al., 2017; Joshanloo & Jovanovic', 2019; Jovanović et al., 2022;), Non-invariance across age has been assigned to several reasons that include (a) differential interpretation of items (Emerson et al., 2017; Erdem, 2022), (b) the sensitivity of items two, four and five to age (Bai et al., 2011; Erdem, 2022; Jang et al., 2017; Hultell & Gustavsson, 2008; Pons et al., 2000), which have also been found to be non-invariant (Jang et al., 2017), (c) the strong wording effect of item four that taps into the past (Bai et al., 2011).

SWLS has shown convergent validity through positive correlations with subjective wellbeing related variables (Bendayan et al., 2013; García-Castro et al., 2022; Ngamaba et al., 2017; Pavot & Diener, 2008; Vázquez et al., 2013) and negative associations with adverse psychological and physical outcomes (e.g. Atienza et al., 2020; Bendayan et al., 2013; García-Castro et al., 2022; López-Ortega, 2016; Lorenzo-Seva et al., 2019; Pavot & Diener, 1993).

The Rationale for the Present Study

In Sri Lanka, locally validated psychological instruments remain limited. Reviews report 55 validated scales by 2013 and 36 additional tools by 2020 (Suraweera et al., 2013; 2020), with only one (WHO-5; World Health Organization (WHO), 1998) assessing wellbeing. Therefore, evaluating the psychometric properties of a translated and adapted SWLS in a Sri Lankan sample is warranted.

Aims of Study and Hypotheses

This study aimed to translate, adapt, and validate the SWLS in a Sri Lankan sample. In line with previous studies, we expected that the translated and adapted version of SWLS (SWLS-SL), would (a) have adequate internal consistency

and test-retest reliability at two weeks; (b) have a one-factor model, (c) show strong measurement invariance across gender but potentially not across age; (d) correlate well with the WHO-5 wellbeing index.

Methods

Participants

Participants were a non-probability sample of 303 persons ($M_{age} = 40.19$ years, $SD = 13.54$, age range = 18 to 79 years; 44.4% male, 54.7 % female and 1.0% transgender) recruited online. More than half the participants had an education level of university degree or higher (55.9%).

Being a structural equation modelling (SEM) technique, CFA requires a large sample (Kline, 2016). The sample size affects parameter estimates, Chi-square tests, and goodness of fit indices (Kyriazos, 2018). However, there is no easy solution to the optimal sample size because it depends on many variables, including the size of the model, the number of parameters to be estimated, and the missing data level (Brown, 2015; Tanaka, 1987; Theodoropoulou, 2021). We used Jackson's (2003) recommended heuristic $N:q$ rule of 20:1, where N is the sample size, and q is the number of parameters to be statistically estimated. Because SWLS has one factor and five indicators, there are 15 parameters, namely five each of factor loadings, intercepts, and error variance, to be statistically estimated. Therefore, a sample size of 300 was planned, which exceeds the minimum required size of 250 (Hu & Bentler, 1999).

Design

The study hypotheses were tested by assessing the psychometric properties of SWLS-SL: the internal consistency, temporal stability, factor structure, measurement invariance across gender

and age groups, and the correlations with WHO-5 scores.

The reliability of the SWLS-SL was measured with Cronbach's α , and test-retest reliability with Pearson's correlation coefficient (r) between the item and scale scores measured two weeks apart.

Item properties were analyzed by estimating the total correlation coefficients without the respective item score. The satisfactory cutoff was 0.30 (De Vaus, 2002, cited in Garcia-Castro et al., 2022).

Factor structure was determined with CFA using IBM SPSS AMOS (Version 22). Model fit was evaluated using maximum likelihood estimation based on covariance matrices (Kline, 2016). This approach was selected because it is appropriate when (a) the data meet the assumption of multivariate normality (Beauducel & Herzberg, 2006), (b) skewness and kurtosis values fall between -1 and $+1$ (Muthén & Kaplan, 1985), and (c) variables have more than five response categories (Dolan, 1994).

Model fit was assessed using multiple indices, interpreted as guidelines rather than strict cutoffs, consistent with recommendations emphasizing close rather than exact fit (Browne & Cudeck, 1992), with RMSEA values of .06–.08 and CFI and TLI values of .90–.95 indicating close fit, $RMSEA \leq .05$ and CFI and $TLI \geq .95$ indicating excellent fit (Hu & Bentler, 1999), and an upper bound of the RMSEA 90% confidence interval below .08 (MacCallum et al., 1996, as cited in Brown, 2015).

Measurement invariance across gender and age groups was assessed using multiple-group confirmatory factor analysis (MG-CFA) (Milfont & Fischer, 2010), following the framework of Byrne (2008) and Brown (2015). First, a single-factor model with five items loading on

self-satisfaction was estimated separately for each group, followed by a combined **configural model** where factor structure was held constant, but factor loadings, intercepts, and residuals were freely estimated. Next, we tested sequentially for **metric invariance** by constraining loadings to be equal, **scalar invariance** by further constraining item intercepts, and **strict invariance** by imposing equality of error variance. At each stage of constraint, the more constrained model was considered tenable if (a) the change in chi-square ($\Delta \chi^2$) was not significant, (b) the change in CFI (Δ CFI) was less than .010, and (c) the change in RMSEA (Δ RMSEA) was less than .015 (Cheung & Rensvold, 2002; Chen, 2007), supplemented with Δ RMSEA less than .015 (Cheung & Rensvold & 2002). When full invariance was not supported, partial invariance was tested by iteratively removing or adding items until acceptable equivalence was achieved, allowing group comparisons based only on invariant items (Brown, 2015; Putnick & Bornstein, 2016).

The convergent validity was assessed with the Pearson correlation coefficient between SWLS-SL and WHO-5 scores. The strength of the correlation was determined as small, moderate, or strong based on the absolute value being around .10, .30, and .50, respectively (Cohen, 1988).

Measures

Three instruments were used.

Demographic Questionnaire

The demographic questionnaire recorded the month and year of birth, sex, and education level.

WHO-5 Wellbeing Index Sinhala Language Version

The WHO-5 Wellbeing Index is a five-item unidimensional scale rated on a six-point scale with reference to the last 14 days (WHO, 1998). The sum of the item scores, converted to a percentage, indicates higher levels of mental wellbeing. The Sinhala language translation has shown good psychometric properties, including good correlation with the Patient Health Questionnaire score and Kessler Psychological Distress Scale (Perera et al., 2020). In the present study, Cronbach's α for the WHO-5 was .93.

SWLS-SL

We followed the seven-step process proposed by Sousa and Rojjanasrirat (2011) to ensure conceptual, semantic, and cultural equivalence between source and target instruments (see also Beaton et al., 2000). In Step 1, two forward translations of the SWLS were produced by bilingual Sinhala-native professionals who were not informed about the back translation (Geisinger, 1994). In Step 2, one researcher compared both translations with the original and synthesized a preliminary Sinhala version. In Step 3, two independent translators back-translated the Sinhala version into English. The researcher reviewed discrepancies; some differences remained.

In Step 4, an expert panel (N = 9) evaluated all versions for equivalence. As a result, "Ideal life" was replaced with "the best life as I think" Similar phrasing has been reported in prior studies (e.g., Bacro et al., 2020; Guhn et al., 2018). "Conditions of my life" was debated but retained. Items 4 and 5 were refined for clarity. The language was maintained at approximately the Grade 8 level, resulting in the pre-final SWLS-SL. In Step 5, 22 mainly monolingual participants reviewed the pre-final version and "if I could live my life over" was revised to a more commonly used expression.

In Step 6, preliminary psychometric properties were assessed in a bilingual sample ($N = 25$), meeting minimum item-to-sample recommendations (Nunnally & Bernstein, 1994). Participants completed the SWLS-SL and the original English version (with item order randomized). Item-level comparisons showed strong correlations with paired-samples t tests ($r = .55-.74$). Mean differences were minimal for Item 5; t tests were nonsignificant for Items 3 and 4, at $p = .01$ for Item 2, and significant for Item 1, indicating partial equivalence. A full psychometric evaluation was conducted with a larger sample in Step 7 (see next section).

Procedure

Online, each participant read the participant information sheet and consented to participate. They then completed the demographic questionnaire, SWLS-SL and WHO-5, presented in that order, read a debriefing and submitted the questionnaires. All questions were made mandatory following Nunnally and Bernstein's (1994) suggestion of enabling participants to answer all questions, thereby avoiding the need for excluding records with missing values (e.g. Bacro et al., 2020; Bai et al., 2011; Bendayan et al., 2013; Gadermann et al., 2010, cited in Bacro et al., 2020; Jovanovic et al., 2022; Vázquez et al., 2013). All participants who made their emails available received the SWLS-SL 13 days after they responded to the survey, requesting them to complete it again the following day.

Participants received no financial or other benefits and participated voluntarily. The study received ethical approval from the Ethics Committee at Arden University, and it conformed with the General Data Protection Regulation 2016 (GDPR) and the Data Protection Act 2018. The data collection took place in 2023 from February 28 to March 19.

Results

Preliminary Analysis

All preliminary analyses were carried out with SPSS (Version 27.0). SWLS-SL item and total scores were treated as continuous variables as the measurement scale was a Likert-type scale with more than five points (Jang et al., 2017). The Q-Q plots and Shapiro-Wilks test for item skewness (-1 to +1) and kurtosis (-3 to +3) provided evidence of normality. Although univariate normality was obtained, multivariate normality was examined because multivariate skewness impacts on tests of means and multivariate kurtosis could severely hamper tests of variances and covariances and distort parameter estimates (Curran et al., 1996). Multivariate kurtosis was 15.65, less than the critical ratio of 16.28. Therefore, data were examined for multivariate outliers using the Mahalanobis Distance test (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2013), which led to the identification and removal of eight multivariate outliers, resulting in an analyzed sample of 303.

For the whole group, the mean total score was relatively high ($M = 25.39$, $SD = 6.62$) out of a possible maximum of 35. The mean score was lowest in the lowest education category ($M = 21.54$, $SD = 6.49$), and highest in the oldest group, 54 to 79 years ($M = 29.30$, $SD = 4.29$). (See Table 1).

Table 1: *SWLS Scores Across Gender, Age, and Education*

Category	n	Mean SWLS	Standard Deviation
Sex			
Male	133	25.76	6.87
Female	167	25.14	6.49
Transgender	3	23.33	1.53
Age group			
18-34	114	24.05	7.27
35-54	134	24.91	6.27
55-79	53	29.30	4.29
Education			
Below GCE O/L	28	21.54	6.49
Up to GCE A/L	55	25.87	6.90
Undergraduate	54	24.42	7.33
Degree or higher	174	26.19	6.11
Total Sample	303	25.39	6.62

Note. ^aAge was unavailable for two participants.

Reliability and Test-Retest Reliability of SWLS-SL

Cronbach's α was .90, indicating good reliability. Overall, all items could be considered good indicators of satisfaction with life. As seen in Table 2, only item 5 caused a marginal increase (from $\alpha = .90$ to $\alpha = .91$) when it was deleted.

Table 2 : *Descriptive Statistics of SWLS -SL Item and Total Scores*

Item	Mean	SD	Skewness	Kurtosis	Corrected item correlation	α if the item is deleted
SWLS-SL1	5.12	1.54	-.95	.07	.79	.87
SWLS-SL2	4.79	1.58	-.73	-.37	.80	.87
SWLS-SL3	5.44	1.46	-1.37	.65	.82	.87
SWLS-SL-4	5.31	1.40	-.96	.32	.78	.88
SWLS-SL5	4.74	1.83	-.95	-.78	.62	.91
Total	25.39	6.63	-.72	-.07		

Of the 195 participants invited to complete the re-test, 73 responded; 14 were excluded due to missing email identifiers, resulting in an analysed sample of $N = 59$. The retest sample was similar in sex composition but was slightly older (Male 45.8%, Female 55.2%; $M_{age} = 48.31$, $SD = 14.0$) compared to the original sample (Male 43.9%, Female 55.1%; $M_{age} = 40.28$, $SD = 13.6$). The two-week retest scores correlated strongly with original scores ($r = .83$, $p < .001$), indicating good temporal stability of SWLS-SL.

Table 3 shows that all inter-item correlations were substantial, with values exceeding .50. Most correlations were $r \leq .70$, with the exception of pairings between items 1 and 2 ($r = .83$) and items 3 and 4 ($r = .80$), suggesting potential item redundancy. Item 5 demonstrated the lowest item correlations, ranging from $r = .54$ to $r = .59$. Overall, the items of SWLS-SL are strongly correlated.

Table 3: *Inter-Item Correlation Matrix of SWLS -SL*

Item	SWLS-SL 1	SWLS-SL 2	SWLS-SL 3	SWLS-SL 4	SWLS-SL 5
SWLS-SL 1	1.00				
SWLS-SL 2	.83	1.00			
SWLS -SL3	.71	.70	1.00		
SWLS-SL 4	.65	.69	.80	1.00	
SWLS-SL 5	.54	.54	.59	.56	1.00

Factorial Structure

The maximum likelihood estimation procedure indicated poor model fit, $\chi^2(5) = 83.75$, $p < .001$, CFI = .93, TLI = .85, and RMSEA = .22, 95% CI [.19, .27]. Modification indices suggested correlating the error terms of items 1 and 2, and items 3 and 4, consistent with the high inter-item correlations observed in Table 3. Allowing these error covariances resulted in a substantial improvement, yielding an excellent fit: $\chi^2(3) = 5.68$, $p = .128$, CFI = 1.00, TLI = .99, and RMSEA = .05, 95% CI [.00, .12].

All items loaded significantly on the latent factor ($p < .001$), with standardized loadings ranging from .67 to .88, exceeding the recommended

minimum of .30 (De Vaus, 2002, as cited in Garcia-Castro et al., 2022). Table 4 reports the factor loadings and error variances, and Figure 1 presents the final model.

Table 4: Factor Loadings and Related Measurement Errors of SWLS-SL Items

Item	Factor loading	Measurement error
1. In most ways my life is close to my ideal.	.80	.64
2. The conditions of my life are excellent.	.81	.85
3. I am satisfied with my life.	.88	.77
4. So far I have gotten the important things I want in life.	.84	.70
5. If I could live my life over, I would change almost nothing.	.67	.45

Note: The items are translated and adapted into the Sinhala language

Figure 1

Schematic depiction of the hypothesized unidimensional factorial structure of the SWLS-SL

Protection Regulation 2016 (GDPR) and the Data Protection Act 2018. The data collection took place in 2023 from February 28 to March 19.

Invariance

Table 5 shows the model fit indices and their changes obtained in the sequential steps of

constraining the models. The tests for invariance supported strict invariance across gender with excellent indices. Across age groups, scalar invariance was supported by all indices except

for a nonsignificant chi-square. Partial strict invariance was not obtained when tested by relaxing the equality of variance constraint of items one by one.

Table 5: Model Fit Indices and Measures of Invariance of SWLS-SL for Sequentially Constrained Models Across Gender and Age Groups

Model	χ^2	df	p	CFI	TLI	$\Delta \chi^2$	p-value of $\Delta \chi^2$	Δ CFI	RMSEA
Gender-Related Invariance									
Configural	14.99	6	.02	.99	.97				.07[.03, .12]
Metric	15.90	10	.10	.99	.99	0.92	.92	.00	.05[.00, .08]
Scalar	18.15	14	.20	.99	.99	2.24	.68	.00	.03[.00, .07]
Strict	28.28	19	.08	.99	.99	10.13	.07	.01	.04[.00, .07]
Age-Related Invariance									
Configural	10.52	6	.10	.99	.99	-		-	.05[.00, .10]
Metric	11.32	10	.33	.99	.99	0.79	.94	.00	.02[.00, .07]
Scalar	2.79	14	.06	.99	.99	11.47	.02	.01	.05[.00, .08]
Strict	50.27	19	.00	.97	.97	7.49	<.001	.02	.07[.05, .10]

Note. χ^2 = Chi-square, df = degrees of freedom, CFI = Comparative Fit Index, TLI = Tucker Lewis

Index, $\Delta \chi^2$ = Change in Chi-square, Δ df = Change in df between successive models, Δ CFI = Change in CFI between successive models. RMSEA = Root mean square error of approximation with 90% confidence interval.

Group Differences in Factor Means

With scalar-level invariance obtained for both groupings, group means were compared (Little, 1997). Independent sample t-tests showed a statistically significant difference between the 18-34 group ($M = 24.05$) and the 35-79 group ($M = 26.21$), $t = 2.74$, $df = 296$, $p = .007$ and no significant difference between men ($M = 25.76$) and women ($M = 25.14$), $t = 0.80$, $df = 298$, $p = .422$.

Convergent Validity

The total scores of SWLS-SL and WHO-5 indicated a statistically significant modest correlation in the expected direction ($r = .36$, $p < .001$). The item correlations varied from .16 to .36, reflecting weak interitem correlations, the

weakest being between item 5 of SWLS-SL and items of WHO-5.

Discussion

The present study translated and adapted the Satisfaction With Life Scale into Sinhalese (SWLS-SL) and evaluated its psychometric properties in a sample of 303 adults recruited online. Our findings provide strong support for the psychometric adequacy of the SWLS-SL in this sample. In line with original validation studies and subsequent research, the scale shows high reliability and test-retest reliability and conforms to the well-established unidimensional factor structure (Álvarez et al., 2018; Amtmann et al., 2019; Bacro et al., 2020).

The present findings indicate strict measurement invariance of the SWLS-SL across gender, extending prior research that has generally supported invariance at or below the scalar level (e.g., Bai et al., 2011; Ghun et al., 2018; Moksnes et al., 2013). Although evidence for age invariance is comparatively limited (Emerson et al., 2017; Jovanović, 2019), the SWLS-SL demonstrate scalar invariance across age groups, consistent with previous findings (e.g., Bacro et al., 2020; Esnaola et al., 2017; Lorenzo-Seva et al., 2019). These results support the equivalence of the scale across gender and age.

Men and women show the same level of satisfaction with life, compared to mixed results in previous studies (Valenti & Faraci, 2024). The slight increase across age is parallel to the finding by Bai et al. (2011), but contrary to other studies (e.g. Jovanović, 2019). These findings imply that while life satisfaction may increase slightly with age, men and women understand and interpret the construct of life satisfaction similarly and have similar satisfaction levels.

The unexpected weak inter-item correlation ($r = .36, p < .001$) between SWLS-SL and WHO-5 scores may be explained by the differences in the philosophical foundations of the two scales (Kusier & Folker, 2021). Four of the five items in WHO-5 refer to feelings or emotions in the past two weeks, stated as I have felt cheerful and in good spirits (Item 1), calm and relaxed (Item 2), active and vigorous (Item 3), fresh and rested (Item 4). In contrast, SWLS items measure cognitive evaluation of life overall, thus capturing different aspects of wellbeing leading to weak inter-item correlations.

Limitations, Strengths, and Future Directions

A key limitation of this study is the lack of a representative Sri Lankan sample. The use of a

non-probability sample, coupled with relatively high educational attainment, limits ecological validity. Data collection was conducted online, restricting participation to individuals with basic digital literacy or access to assistance, which may have introduced sampling bias.

Despite these limitations, the study has notable strengths. It employed a rigorous translation and cultural adaptation process in line with recommended guidelines (Sousa & Rojjanasrirat, 2011), extending beyond basic translation and back-translation procedures, which may produce suboptimal target-language versions (Geisinger, 1994; International Test Commission, 2017). This rigour likely enhanced conceptual, semantic, and cultural equivalence between the original English SWLS and the Sinhala version, contributing to the observed strong psychometric properties. For example, in the present study, the relatively weaker performance of item 5 did not compromise overall scale invariance, unlike in previous studies (Arrindell et al., 2022; Bai et al., 2011; Hultell et al., 2008; Pons et al., 2000).

Future research could extend these findings using representative samples and include validation in the Tamil language to establish broader applicability in Sri Lanka. Further assessment of convergent validity with other measures of subjective well-being is warranted. In addition, differential item functioning—particularly for Items 4 and 5—could be examined to clarify and reduce potential bias associated with past-oriented and strongly worded items (Schutte et al., 2019).

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